

“FUNKSIYA XOSILASI” MAVZUSINI O’RGANISHDA KLASTER MODELIDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada o’rta maktablarning 11-sinflarida o’qitiladigan “xosilani xisoblash usullari” modulini o’qitishda innovatsion klaster metodidan foydalanishga yondoshuv masalasi ko’rib chiqilgan. Bunday yondoshuvning pedagogik va didaktik tamoillari ilmiy asosda shakllantirilgan. Shuningdek inovatsion klaster metodining matematika fanini o’qitishdagi afzalliklari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: Klaster metodi, xosila, foydalanish, usullar, matematika, o’qitish, funksiya.

“Ta’lim to’g’risida”gi va “Kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturi to’g’risida”gi O’zbekiston Respublikasi qonunlariga, 2017-2021-yillarga mo’ljallangan “O’zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo’yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi”, 2018 yil 5 sentabrdagi “Xalq ta’limi tizimiga boshqaruvning yangi tamoyillarini joriy etish chora tadbirlari to’g’risida”gi PQ-3931-sonli qarori,

shuningdek O’zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017 yil 6 apreldagi “Umumiy o’rta va o’rta maxsus, kasbhunar ta’limining davlat ta’lim standartlarini tasdiqlash to’g’risida”gi 187-sonli qaroriga muvofiq, ta’lim bosqichlarining uzluksizligi va izchilligini ta’minlash, ta’limningzamonaviy metodologiyasini yaratishni yanada takomillashtirishni taqozo etadi. Bunday muammoni hal etish mavzu bo’yicha uslubiy, didaktik va varitiv yondashuvlarni bir tizimga keltirib, interaktiv tizim orqali mavzuni o’qitish tavsiya etiladi. Bu yo’nalishdagi ilmiy izlanishlar shuni ko’rsatadiki, mavzuni tizimli o’rgatishda ta’limning klaster metodidan foydalanish yuqori samara beradi. So’ngi yillarda jaxon miqyosida ta’limning klaster metodi, o’zining mohiyati jihatidan, umumta’lim maktablarida matematika fanini samrasini bermoqda. Respublikamizda bu yo’nalishda pedagogika oliy – o’quv yurtlari bilan bir qatorda ilmiy markazlar, o’qituvchilar malaka oshirish markazlari bilan hamkorlikda izlanishlar olib bormoqdalar. Matematika fanini o’qitishda klaster metodini qo’llash asnosida bu fanning xususiyatidan kelib chiqqan holda uni “loyihalab” o’qitish uslubini o’qituvchi yaxshi bilishi kerak. Umumta’lim maktablarining yuqori sinflarida (10- 11 sinflarda) matematik analiz elementlari

– funksiya xosilasi, aniqmas integrali va aniq integrali mavzulari o’rgatiladi.

Zamonaviy ta’limda klaster metodlarini qo’llash ta’lim sifat va samaradorligiga ijobiy ta’sir o’tkazadi. Jumladan matematika fanlarini o’qitish metodikasida uning bazaviy bo’limlarining klaster modellarini ishlab chiqish va undan o’quv jarayonlarida foydalanish Oliy ta’limdagi dolzarb masalalardan biri xisoblanadi. Funksiyaning nuqtadagi xosilasi $y = f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda aniqlangan bo’lsin. (a, b) intervalga tegishli x_0 va $x_0 + \Delta x$ nuqtalarni olamiz.

$y = f(x)$ funksiyaning bu nuqtalardagi qiymatlari $f(x_0)$ va $f(x_0 + \Delta x)$ dan funksiyaning $\Delta y = f(x_0 + \Delta x) - f(x_0)$ orttirmasini tuzamiz. y argument Δx ga o’zgariganda funksiya qanchaga o’zgarishini ko’rsatadi.

1.1- Rasm. “Funktsiya xosilasi” mavzusini o‘rganishning klaster modeli

1.2- Rasm. “Funktsiya xosilasi” mavzusi klaster modeling tashkil etuvchilari

Klaster metodida xosila olish usuli doirasida yechiladigan misollar majmuasi shakllantiriladi. Ya’ni misol va masalalar majmuasini metodlarga mos belgilar asosida sinflarga ajratiladi. Keyingi bosqichda boshqa funksiyalar sinflanishli gruxlarga ajratib, klaster metodi asosida unga mos usullarini qo‘llash mavzuni o‘rganishda yaxlitlikni ta’minlaydi. Bu esa o‘quvchilarda matematik masalalarni yechishda mustaqil fikrlash va to‘g‘ri qaror qabul qilishga yordam beradi.

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